

HIGH SCHOOL STUDENT ABILITY AND PROBLEMS OF ITS DETERMINATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7708326>

Abstract. *In this article, the ability of a high school student and the problems of its determination are theoretically analyzed. In this, thoughts are given about the origin and diagnosis of abilities and the influence of the social environment on the formation of abilities .*

Keywords: *interest, ability, mental thinking, intellectual competence, psychodiagnostics.*

Humanity has been and will continue to be the main subject of social and humanitarian sciences. Because the complete structure of man, his abilities, talents, etc. have not been fully revealed.

It is known that ability is not innate, but arises as a result of being born with some organic advantage. Skills that develop from early childhood include music and drawing. In other words, through interest in art, ability is developed and other aspects of it are revealed. The first manifestations of aptitude for learning science begin in early childhood. Talented young people who made discoveries in science, mostly under the age of 20, were all mathematicians.

We should not forget the influence of the social environment in the formation of abilities. For example, all 17 talented musicians from the Bach family were born and grew up in a musical family.

When a group of gifted (talented) and normal children were examined in Russia at the age of 9-10 using R.B. Ketgell's child-adapted personality questionnaire, the following statistical differences were found: gifted children are more highly intelligent, tense and frustrated, reactive and excitable, dominant, independent, self-centered comparing to others, courageous and risk-taking, irresponsible and conflicted, their behavior is bad managers. Among ordinary children, mostly intelligent, restrained, faithful, thoughtful, hardworking, good understanding of norms, balanced and relaxed people came out. In addition, gifted children have been found to be withdrawn, self-confident, shy and restless.

Talented boys were characterized by tendencies of behavior: dominance, low level of self-control, irresponsibility. In girls, emotional - restlessness, stubbornness, quick anger, shyness, self-doubt were observed. Despite the fact that gifted children, unlike normal children, have a high energy potential, it is a critical zone and is included among the factors of maladaptation of the characteristics of gifted children.

The ability is very likely to be present in every child. But there are several factors that prevent this ability from being noticed and developed. In particular, a situation that occurs in most Uzbek families is that mothers are entrusted with household chores along with child rearing. Many women try to do work faster and better, and pay little attention to the issue of their children's studies and interests. However, their children may have real abilities or talents.

Sometimes it is seen that gifted children hardly get grades in different subjects. It can be seen that they spend a lot of time puzzling over trivial matters. It is also evident that they are almost inseparable from ordinary children. But they are still capable, it is enough to apply an individual approach to them.

In our science, there are also individuals with autistic diagnosis who have very strong abilities, but who have gone into themselves. It is very difficult to get into a relationship with people with such abilities. Mostly in kindergartens and schools, they sit alone in out-of-sight places. It is very difficult for them to answer verbally. Memory and calculation skills will be 5-6 times stronger than those of their peers. According to reports, Einstein was also autistic. Many academics and professors agree with this diagnosis. Regular activities of psychotherapists with such people can realize some aspects of socialization. This is practically guaranteed to give positive results.

Ability is a characteristic with a sign of socially conditioned development, formation. But some parents force their children to do too many activities and lessons to make them talented from a young age. Especially at the age of 3-4, children's activities are not focused on learning, but on playing. Failure to take into account the child's interests and problems and forced lessons (especially at the age of 3-4) can lead to mental disorders.

In some situations, even without parental guidance, it is observed in life that a child has an interest and ability in science. But the child's social status and life can prevent him from developing his abilities. In such situations, it is natural for a child to try to help his family instead of studying and gaining knowledge. Ability, however, withers and fades without practice. That is why the environment in the family ensures the development of the child, and the role of the family, especially the parents, is incomparable in the growth of his existing opportunities and mental thinking, abilities, and intellectual potential.

It is known that a gifted person acquires knowledge and skills, profession easily and quickly, he shows great diligence due to his interest, which creates additional opportunities for his study and work to be more effective.

A passionate person devotes all his energy and time to the work he loves. Otherwise, the activity would be unnatural and illogical. Many talented people have put hard work and hard work in the first place when evaluating their success. Evaluating the role of talent and hard work in his success, Edison said that only 1 percent was genius and 99 percent was sweat. In general, it is clear that all great people, having great diligence and hard work, even if their nervous systems were naturally weak, subjectively assessed their achievements as a result of work and not ability. It can be said that diligence is the basis of work, and the resulting diligence and hard work is the basis of productive activity, that is, the ground for the manifestation and development of abilities.

Even when a person chooses one specific activity as his main life activity, his comprehensive development is the reason for achieving high success in this activity. Many great writers, as shown above, were famous only as professional writers, but they turned to drawing, painting and music as a tool to help create clearer, more vivid, vivid literary images.

For example, we know that Repin's understanding of music and his passionate love for it, musical images helped him to create bright artistic paintings.

The fact that a person is fully developed makes it possible to more accurately assess his capabilities and determine his main activity accordingly. In addition, it ensures the development of all abilities, all of which together produce an extremely high effect even in one specific activity, compared to the effect of one ability in this activity. *If ability is an "ensemble" of a person's characteristics, then the highest levels of talent - talent and genius - are an "ensemble" of highly developed abilities of a person.*

The highest level of ability is called "**talent**". *Talent is a combination of natural talent and ability that allows a person to perform some complex activity successfully, independently and*

*in a unique way. The people themselves have a saying about talent, "God gave." In turn, skill is formed when natural talent, ability, talent is combined with life professional experience and excellent work. If the highest manifestation of ability is called "talent", then the highest manifestation of talent is greatness. **Greatness** is the manifestation of human creative power at a high level. The German philosopher Schopenhauer says about this: "A sniper who hits a target that no one has seen is a talent, a sniper who hits a target that no one has seen is great."*

High school students differ from each other in their abilities. The ability develops unevenly, a temporary stoppage of development often alternates with rapid development. This situation requires individualization, special pedagogic delicacy. Sometimes it is necessary to impose excessive demands on some people and give them additional tasks, while others should be helped so that their abilities develop faster, they become more filled with knowledge, necessary characteristics and compensatory (restorative) mechanisms are formed. It should be remembered that among physically healthy and mentally healthy students there are no incompetents, but among them there are only those for whom we do not know what they are capable of. For this reason, an optimistic approach to studying students consistently and assessing their abilities is a necessary quality of ability educators and coaches.

Life experience and analysis of pedagogic-psychological literature show that ability is manifested and developed in a certain consistency. First of all, musical ability is realized, all great musicians knew how to play tunes successfully from the age of 4-5. After that, at the age of 6-8, the ability to paint appears. It is possible to observe that children of this age make colorful original drawing samples. Exhibitions of artistic works of talented children are common in the world experience.

Therefore, in the presence of certain natural opportunities, all-round development is the main condition for the development of true talent and genius. Even in the absence of obvious natural opportunities, the comprehensive development of a person ensures that a person's abilities develop to a higher degree than the one chosen by him and achieve relatively high indicators in his activity.

Knowing the identity of the student leads to effective results in education. The theoretical and practical work being carried out in this regard cannot be said to be at the level of the requirements of the time. This has a negative impact on the effectiveness of activities in the field of personal development of the student.

CONCLUSION

So, first of all, it is necessary to know the student's interests very well. The direction of the student's personality is formed by his needs, interests, passions and ideals. On the other hand, yuu characteristics mean student's relationship to existence, events of social life, society, team, other persons and himself. In order for educational activities to be effective, the teacher needs to have clear information about each student's goals, scope of interest, attitude to career choice, work, and self-development.

Naturally, all the student's interests are related to his cognitive activity. *Attention, intuition, perception, memory, imagination, thinking* are involved in the process of knowing . Therefore, if the teacher does not have psychological knowledge and experience, he will not notice the opportunities and changes in the personality and mentality of the student in time, and will not be able to choose the right method for their development based on analysis.

In addition, the teacher should pay serious attention to the mental and physical capabilities of each student, the family environment and the peculiarities of education in it, and the measures taken to direct the student's personality to a certain field.

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